

Motives and attitudes when choosing the medical profession among the first-course students at the Medical University – Sofia in the 2024/2025 academic year

Vidin Kirkov¹, Kremena Ivanova¹

¹ Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Vidin Kirkov (vkirkov@foz.mu-sofia.bg)

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Abstract

The choice of a profession largely determines the life path of an individual, the development of his individual qualities and abilities, the development of his essential powers, and his realization as a labor and social being. The labor and professional path influences the overall social behavior and social activity of the individual. The choice of the medical profession is a complex decision-making process in which many subjective and objective factors are intertwined. Accordingly, this article presents and analyzes data from an empirical study investigating the motives and attitudes when choosing the medical profession among first-year students at the Medical University – Sofia during the academic year 2024/2025.

Keywords

motives, attitudes, students, medical profession, professional development

Introduction

The issues related to the choice of occupation (profession) were also of concern to the ancient Greek philosophers Socrates and Plato and the French thinkers Pascal, Voltaire, and Rousseau. They were the subject of attention of representatives of a variety of philosophical, educational, economic, and other schools and teachings, from the humanism of the Renaissance to rationalism in the era of the initial accumulation of capital (Vodenitcharov 1986, 1992).

The profession is perhaps the only area in which the individual and society are closely and inseparably intertwined. The historical development and the stages of demographic transition through which humanity has passed convincingly show that the professional division of labor

aims to achieve the fullest realization of people through their professional specialization and their best unification within a certain socio-economic formation (Kirkov 2025).

An individual's need for self-affirmation is tightly linked with his professional and labor activity and with the successful realization of it. For this reason, the professional choice is a complex decision-making process, determined by social and personal factors, since it is dictated not only by the needs of society but also by individual interests, opportunities, needs, and inclinations (Kirkov et al. 2024).

The choice of a profession turns out to be a complex knot in which the interaction between the individual and society is intertwined. In this case, the existing mechanisms for managing and regulating the reproduction of labor potential are also put to the test through the choice

of profession, education systems, professional guidance and selection, qualification and retraining of the workforce, etc. Just as today's requirements are far higher, in the future, social, scientific, and technical development will place even greater demands on the processes of professional self-determination and the formation of youth.

For professional orientation, the health of the individual is of great importance, which is manifested directly through health contraindications for choosing a profession and indirectly – when determining the psychophysiological requirements for certain specialists. In this regard, the main problem for adolescents is prevention, which includes their development, training, morbidity, professional selection, nutrition, and the fight against alcoholism, smoking, and other risk factors. In this sense, the relationship between health and profession should be considered bidirectionally. Health is not only a prerequisite and an opportunity for a certain profession but also a result, a consequence of this professional activity. The main task is for the profession to be a factor in preserving and improving the health potential of the individual and, based on this, to improve its multifaceted development (Lyndon et al. 2017; Smith et al. 2017; Zawislak et al. 2023).

Needs, interests, goals, and value orientation are constituent elements of the motivational process. They are in dynamic interaction, and the motive appears as their integral whole. Motives depend on both the characteristics of the individual and the specific situation and can be contradictory and inconsistent, since the motivational process is multifactorial and dynamic (Vodenitcharov 1986; Avramova et al. 2014). The leading motives that determine the decision to apply for a specialty in medicine can generally be grouped into two main groups:

1. Humane – treating sick people and protecting the health of society (humane and noble profession).
2. Motives related to the realization of the personality – a prestigious profession, ensuring financial stability, ensuring the independence of the practitioner, and the opportunity for the best manifestation of personal abilities.

The purpose of this article is to present and analyze the motives and attitudes when choosing the medical profession of first-year medical students at the Medical University – Sofia in the 2024/2025 academic year.

Materials and methods

The object of research was first-year medical students at the Medical University – Sofia in the academic year 2024/2025.

The study was conducted during the period December 2024–January 2025 in the city of Sofia and included 189 medical students, whereby the percentage ratio of male to female participants was 47.60% to 52.40%.

A wide range of sociological and statistical methods are used in the survey: the documentary method; the questionnaire survey method – medical students from MU – Sofia were surveyed using an independently developed questionnaire card; descriptive analysis; analysis of variance; Pearson's χ^2 test; and graphical analysis for visualizing the results obtained. The indicators were assessed at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance.

The quantitative analyses were performed using the SPSS 17.0 statistical software package. Microsoft Office products were used for tabular and graphical processing and presentation.

Results and discussion

In connection with the increased and growing demands from society for the personal qualities of a physician, the need to analyze the process of applying to higher medical schools and the process of formation of medical personnel is becoming increasingly acute. For the academic year 2024/2025 at the Medical University – Sofia, for the specialty „Medicine,“ a total of 1,503 candidate students applied, with six women and three men competing for one place. The present study covers 189 first-year students, of whom 47.60% were men and 52.40% were women, out of a total of 230 accepted for training. The philosophy related to higher medical education, the requirements for admission to the university, and the procedures related to the selection of students undoubtedly have an impact on their socio-demographic profile. Fig. 1 presents the age of Bulgarian first-year students, with the majority being 18, 19, or 20 years old, which indicates that they applied immediately after completing their secondary education. Moreover, 87% of them applied for the first time to MU – Sofia (Fig. 2) (Ministry of Health 2021; Regulations for the organization and activities of Medical University – Sofia 2024).

In Bulgarian higher education, in the 1960s, the quota principle for student admission was introduced in order to ensure equal representation by gender in different professional fields. The reason for quotas in the admission of students to medical universities (50% men and 50% women) is the need to maintain gender balance within

Figure 1. Age of first-year Medicine students.

Figure 2. How many times did you apply?

the profession. This avoids the dominance of one gender in certain specialties – for example, internists and pediatricians are more often women, while surgical specialties are dominated by men. The even representation of doctors of both sexes makes it possible to provide different perspectives and approaches to medical practice and communication with patients. It is known that women show more empathy, apply a holistic approach, and communicate better with patients, while men tend to perform better in specialties requiring more physical strength and endurance. Excessive feminization in medicine, on the other hand, can cause problems with the provision of human resources in specialties that demand endurance and technical skills. Both genders can successfully perform in such areas, but having enough men ensures the profession has the necessary mix of abilities. Gender-balanced teams exhibit better dynamics and psychological and emotional stability, which, in specialties with high levels of stress and intense decision-making, leads to better outcomes for patients (Vodenitcharov 1986; Law on Higher Education in the Republic of Bulgaria 2022; Kirkov 2023).

Considering that such a significant life decision as the choice of a profession occurs in late adolescence or early youth, special attention should be paid to the motives and mechanism of realization of the professional choice in future doctors. That is why we asked the following questions in the empirical study. Fig. 3 shows that 62% of the respondents decided to apply for “Medicine” during their high school course of study, 29% during junior high school, and only 9% after graduating from high school. These results indicate that the process of making a decision about a future career requires sufficient time to understand the priorities and long-term consequences associated with the profession.

The majority of participants in the study (81%) indicated that they independently chose the medical profession (Fig. 4). Independence in choosing the medical profession reflects not only a mature approach by this specific cohort of youth to solving vital personal and public issues but also, in some cases, a demonstration of “freedom of will.” As shown in Fig. 5, the majority of respondents – 65% – have a family member working in the medical profession. Parental and familial support is a unique and long-term process expressed through either deliberate

Figure 3. When did you decide to choose Medicine as a profession?

Figure 4. Who influenced you to choose „Medicine“?

Figure 5. Do you have a close relative (mother, father, siblings, etc.) in the medical profession?

and purposeful activity or spontaneous and unforced influences. The specifics of family life, traditions in family professions, and conversations within the home environment contribute to the formation of a “collective” decision regarding the choice of a medical career. The spontaneous, unintentional influence of the family environment – exercised through casual conversations and tolerant discussions – often has a more profound effect than overt pressure from relatives. Parents may also exert deliberate influence by highlighting the social prestige and advantages of the medical profession in a way that aligns with the individual characteristics of the candidate. As a result

of such influences, the behavior of a young family member crossing the “threshold of life” may exhibit a tendency toward “independence” in making the final decision, wherein parental influence becomes internalized and is perceived as a personal conclusion. At the same time, the adolescent period is characterized by increased cognitive and value-driven activity, heightened emotional sensitivity, and marked psychological instability.

The final question of the empirical study examined the primary motives for choosing the medical profession among first-year students, categorized into two main groups: humane motives and motives related to personal realization. The results show that the majority of respondents – 86%, or 162 participants – were guided by humane motives in their choice, specifically the desire to treat the sick and protect public health. These students emphasized that medicine is a “humane and noble profession.” The second group of motives relates to personal development. Within this group, the most frequently cited motive was the “prestige of the profession,” noted by approximately 53% (100 participants), followed by “ensuring financial stability” (35%) and “professional independence” (18%). It is important to emphasize that the prestige of the medical profession stems from it being one of the oldest professions, born of humanity’s essential need for health. At the same time, the individual prestige of the physician depends greatly on the personal qualities of the medical professional – on the personality of the doctor (Soethout 2008; Vodenitcharov 1992, 2021; Kirkov 2023).

Figure 6. What are your main motives for choosing „Medicine“?

Inferences and conclusions

Based on the results of an empirical study on the motives and attitudes when choosing the medical profession among first-year students at MU–Sofia in the academic year 2024/2025, we come to the conclusion that the choice of the medical profession is a complex decision-making process in which many subjective and objective factors are intertwined. When choosing the medical profession, the guiding principle should be “the well-being of humanity, as well as one’s own improvement,” because in order to give meaning and a certain direction to the lives of those who have chosen this profession, it should have a noble long-term goal. This may remove many of the distress-causing disappointments and

doubts related to the choice and daily actions and will undoubtedly give a certain significance to the efforts of doctors.

The choice of a profession largely determines the life path of an individual, the development of his individual qualities and abilities, the deployment of his essential forces, and his realization as a labor and social being. The labor and professional path influences the overall social behavior and social activity of the personality. Educational and professional plans are the most important components of the life plans of youth. In their totality, they are an expression of its social orientation – through them, the aspirations of young people to occupy a certain „place in life“ are manifested. Orientation to the spheres of education and professional work is formed under the influence of the real significance of these spheres in the life of society. Moreover, the main subjective criterion on the basis of which the educational and professional plans of youth are formed, and the choice of a profession is carried out in general, is the value orientation of the personality. Higher education offers relatively the best opportunities for harmonious development and realization and ensures a high professional and general cultural level. On the threshold of their independent lives, young people immediately realize the life prospects that higher education can provide them as a field and means for realization, self-improvement, and gaining high social prestige.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

Both authors have contributed equally.

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Avramova N, Yaneva K, Bonev B (2014) First-year dental students' motivation and attitudes for choosing the dental profession. *Acta Medica Academica* 43(2):113–121. <https://doi.org/10.5644/ama2006-124.110>
- Han ER, Yeo S, Kim MJ, Lee YH, Park KH, Roh H (2019) Medical education trends for future physicians in the era of advanced technology and artificial intelligence: an integrative review. *BMC Medical Education* 19(1): 460. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-019-1891-5>
- Kirkov V (2023) A training quality optimisation model for the undergraduate internship in Medical university – Sofia, Sofia 2023. PhD Thesis, Medical University of Sofia.
- Kirkov V (2024) The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the quality of higher medical education. *Pharmacia* 71: 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.71.e128039>
- Kirkov V (2025) Trends in postgraduate professional orientation of young doctors graduated from the Medical University-Sofia. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e146974>
- Kirkov V, Vodenicharova A, Ivanova K, Markova K (2024) Trends and motives in the post-graduate professional orientation of the young doctors of the 2023 class of Medical University-Sofia. *Pharmacia* 71: 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.71.e138245>
- Kirkov V, Zlatanova-Velikova R (2022) Approaches and methods for quality assurance of medical education in Bulgaria regulated in normative documents. *Man, society medicine, Kardzhali*, 2022, 380–386.
- Kirkov V, Zlatanova-Velikova R, Vodenicharova A, Leventi N (2022) Quality of the practical education during undergraduate internship at the Medical university Sofia. *Acta Medica Bulgarica Journal XLIX 4/2022*: 48–53. <https://doi.org/10.2478/amb-2022-0042>
- Kumwenda B, Cleland J, Prescott G, Walker K, Johnston P (2019) Relationship between sociodemographic factors and specialty destination of UK trainee doctors: a national cohort study. *BMJ Open* 9: e026961. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-026961>
- Law on Higher Education in the Republic of Bulgaria (2022) Law on Higher Education in the Republic of Bulgaria. <https://lex.bg/laws/ldoc/2133647361>
- Lyndon MP, Henning MA, Alyami H, Krishna S, Yu TC, Hill AG (2017) The Impact of a Revised Curriculum on Academic Motivation, Burnout, and Quality of Life Among Medical Students. *Journal of Medical Education and Curricular Development* 4: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2382120517721901>
- Ministry of Health (2021) Ministry of Health – Republic of Bulgaria. National Health Strategy 2021–2030. <https://www.mh.government.bg/bg/politiki/strategii-i-kontseptsii/strategii/proekt-na-nacionalna-zdravna-strategiya-2030/>
- Regulations for the organization and activities of Medical University-Sofia (2024) Regulations for the organization and activities of Medical University-Sofia. <https://mu-sofia.bg/za-universiteta/normativni-dokumenti/pravilnici-mu/>
- Smith V, Bethune C, Hurley K (2017) Examining Medical Student Specialty Choice Through a Gender Lens: An Orientational Qualitative Study. *Teaching and learning in medicine* 30: 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10401334.2017.1306447>
- Soethout MBM, Heymans MW, Olle J (2008) Career preference and medical students' biographical characteristics and academic achievement, *Medical Teacher* 30(1): e15–e22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01421590701759614>
- UNESCO (1989) International Conference on Education. 41st session. Higher Education Policy and Strategy and its Diversification, Paris.
- Vallerand RJ, Pelletier LG, Blais MR, Brière NM, Senecal C, Vallières EF (1992) The Academic Motivation Scale: A measure of intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivation in education. *Educational and Psychological Measurement* 52: 1003–1017. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164492052004025>
- Vodenitcharov Tz (1986) Profession doctor. *Medicine and physical education*.
- Vodenitcharov Tz (1992) *Way in medicine*, Sofia.
- Vodenitcharov Tz (2018) *Beyond the Limits of the Possible*. GorexPress.
- Vodenitcharov Tz, Borisov V (2021) *The Public Health Phenomenon in a Changing World*, Second Revised Edition. Gorex Press, 229.
- WHO [World Health Organization] (2019) The Global Action Plan for Healthy Lives and Well-being for All (SDG3 GAP). <https://www.who.int/initiatives/sdg3-global-action-plan>
- WHO [World Health Organization] (1996) WHOQOL-BREF. Introduction, Administration, Scoring and Generic Version of the Assessment. Field Trial Version December 1996. Programme on Mental Health, World Health Organization, Geneva. 1996, December. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHOQOLBREF>
- Zawiślak D, Skrzypiec K, Żur-Wyrozumska K, Habera M, Cebula G (2023) Academic Motivation and Quality of Life of Polish Medical Students. *Folia Medica Cracoviensia* 63(4): 63–80. <https://doi.org/10.24425/fmc.2023.148759>